

Assessing the Impact of Easy and Restrictive Macroeconomic Policies on Ecological Footprint Index in Asian Economies

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 26, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 31, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Fiscal Policy, Monetary Policy, ADC Environmental Quality, Ecological Footprint (ECFP)</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6334929</p>	<p><i>In recent decades, all the literature on the mental problems of the environmental economy and their causes calls for immediate action when it comes to environmental contamination. In this setting, this paper expands the literature with developing a new model connecting macroeconomic policies, gross domestic per capita consumption, fossil fuel consumption, consumption of renewable energy, and Ecological Footprint (ECFP) for the Asian economies from 1996 to 2020. The results of Westerlund cointegrating tests confirm the long-term association of the variables. The two-step system GMM estimators discover the following key results. First, easy fiscal policy exacerbates the negative consequences of environmental quality. However, restrictive fiscal policy is an effective measure aimed at reducing the adverse effects of environmental quality. Secondly, both easy and contracting monetary policies are deteriorating and improving the quality of the environment, respectively. Third, overall consumer spending and fossil fuel spending are positively associated with pollution. Fourth, renewable power improves air quality by disrupting environmental quality. The causative affiliation among the variables was also confirmed through the application of the Granger causality test. The article suggests some significant implications for authorities to develop effective policies and plans to improve environmental quality in line with current results.</i></p>

Introduction

In recent decades, empirical research has identified many factors in the quality of the environment. Except for a few, all of these studies warned of the growing threat of climate change, such as rising temperatures and climate variances (Chishti et al. (2020) and Grim et al. (2008)). The past ten years (2010-2019) are considered the warmest decade, and 2017 was the hottest year over the past 40 years (World Meteorological Organization (2019)). Empires presently support an academic agreement that the expanding proportion of environmental quality, among different determinants, represents an intense danger to the climate (Adedoyin et al. (2020) and Malik et al., 2016). As per the observations of the U.S. The Ecological footprint network (2021) reported that ecological footprint division by the number of earths since the 1996 as demonstrated in Figure 1. Consequently, the global climate is subject to several variations, namely reducing polar ice caps, sea-level rise and extended seasons, and global precipitation oscillations (Usman et al. 2020 and Bilgili et al. 2016). Consequently, global climate change and its effects have attracted considerable attention from researchers. In addition, exploring predictors of environmental quality has become the primary area of research for environmentalists (Ulah et al., 2020, All-Mulalli et al., 2012 and Singh and Dhadsa, 2021).

Figure. 1 Global Footprint Network Outlook (Number of Earths) from 1996 to 2020

Source: Global Footprint Network (2021)

Worldwide, environmental quality is prevalently brought about by the burning of fossil fuels that drive monetary development also: a view that is held by most researchers (Sarvanan et al. 2018, 2020 and Landman 2010). For the most part, the bit of petroleum derivative usage stands 80% of all fuel-making sources beginning in 2018 (International Energy Agency 2020). Just as energy usage redesigns the individual fulfilment and monetary advancement, policymakers need to regulate energy portfolios so much that it addresses a little peril to the environment (Georgantopolous et al. (, 2012). Inhabitants of essentially every economy by and large eat up an essential portion (60 discharges 70%) of their Gross Domestic Product (Bahmane-Oskoe et al. (2015). Thus, by ADC (Aggregate per capita domestic consumption spending), the usage of petroleum products for energy creation ends up being more genuine, i.e., continuous development popularity is enhanced by an interminable expansion in FFC (Fossil fuel combustion), raising Carbon dioxide emanations (Ahmed and Khattak, 2002). Jeble et al. (2020) and Balouch et al. (2019) believed that along with growth at the local and worldwide level, it is essential to keep up the excellent environmental quality. The researchers accentuate implementing environmentally friendly energy because of quickly expanding expected climatic dangers during the most recent couple of years. Sustainable power utilization REC (Renewable Energy Consumption) assumes an essential part in improving the climatic quality by diminishing the decaying impacts of Environmental quality (Caglar, 2020; ORyan et al. (2020), Ullah et al. (2020). Notwithstanding, new businesses be reluctant to put resources into innovations for Renewable energy consumption and likei to utilize cheap production techniques dependent on Fossil Fuel Combustion (Ahmad and Khattak 2020) because of the absence of information (Liu et al., 2020). Furthermore, EMP (easy monetary policy) and RMP (restrictive monetary policies) are critical indicators of Environmental quality. Qingquan et al. (2020) declared that an EMP (lower real interest rate) and RMP (increasing real rate of interest) grow and reduce industrial output, respectively. Consequently, fossil fuel combustion resources are implemented, prompting expansion and diminishing the measure of Environmental quality. Regarding the unique circumstance, our study focuses on the Chinese and Indian economies for empirical investigation because of the following reasons. First and foremost, these economies have essentially numerous essential attributes, consisting of huge inhabitants (practically 40% of the world population), non-industrial nations with a quick development rate, and the tendency for accepting the worldwide market (Azevedo et al. (2018). These countries have also achieved outstanding financial achievements over the past 60 years. They have more potential than the G6 (US, UK, Italy, France and Germany) to lead overall sensible improvement in the upcoming 40 years (Wilson and Purushothaman 2003). Over time, Pao and Tasai (2010) project that these economies will have a higher GDP by 2050 than the G7.

The Gross Domestic Product of these economies was documented as \$11.8 trillion, which was 20% of the overall economies' gross product. (Zhang and Wange, 2019). To accomplish supportable financial development, these economies need to strongly rely upon a great deal of fuel source use that produces a massive measure of Environmental quality, as Fig. 3 outlines the general situation of per-capita fossil fuel byproducts in Chinese and Indian nations. Beginning in 2014, China stays at the top by conveying twenty-nine per cent and India at the minor circumstance by creating one per cent of the world's Carbon dioxide discharge, among carbon-sending 'Asian economies', as Fig. 2 addresses the whole situation. Henceforth, 'CCAC (Climate and Clean Air Coalition), 'GCR (Global Climate Report) of 2019 alerts that 93% of the all-out people should bear the exigency of extreme contamination by 2030 if the simple measures and arrangements are not implemented on a pressing

premise. Subsequently, it stays an examination basic to investigate the endogenous just as exogenous determinants, which may debase the natural quality.

Though numerous variables that influence the natural quality have been investigated in the most recent twenty years, the present study thinks about the fiscal arrangement as an innovative and unmonitored factor of natural deterioration on account of the accompanying clarification by considering the Ecological Footprint (ECFP) as a measure of environmental quality. Governments execute the fiscal arrangements through taxes and government spending to control unemployment, rising prices, and economic development. The tax proportion arrangements transform the fiscal arrangements into EFP (Easy Fiscal Policy) and RFP (restrictive Fiscal Policy). The easy fiscal policy presents a condition wherein the public authority expands its spending and reduces taxes that boost consumers' DPI (Disposable personal income) ADC (aggregate per capita domestic consumption spending). The extension in ADC puts weight on homegrown organizations to create merchandise at a lower cost. Firms use filthy and eco-unpleasant methods during creation to deal with the items' interest and homegrown rivalry.

Figure: 2 Environmental qualities (%) of Chinese and Indian economies in 2019

Source: World Bank (2019)

It summarizes a decline in taxes through Easy Fiscal Policy increases aggregate per capita domestic consumption spending (ADC), industrial output, non-renewable energy source utilization, and increased environmental quality. On the opposite side, Restrictive Fiscal Policy shows a condition where the public authority diminishes its spending or raises taxes, decreasing the personal disposable income of the consumer (DPI) and ADC. The restrictive fiscal policy reduces the limit of organizations to produce more output. To evade this issue, firms cut their yield and non-sustainable power source usage during the creation interaction, resulting in decreased carbon dioxide discharge (Ahmad and Khattak, 2020). To summarize, a restrictive fiscal policy diminishes ADC, industrial output, and non-renewable energy source utilization and diminishes environmental quality. Since the Chinese and Indian nations utilize the fiscal arrangement as an entire apparatus for achieving development, FDI (foreign capital flows), and advancement, it requires assessing its viability to improve environmental quality.

Figure: 3 The ECFP scenario for Asian Economies

Source: Global Footprint Network (2021)

The current article analyzes the potential impacts of easy and restrictive macroeconomic policies (fiscal and monetary) on ecological footprint (ECFP) in Asian economies for the period from 1996 to 2020. Subsequently, the novelty of the study from the existing literature lies in as follows:

1. This analysis offers the primary macroeconomic model, which investigates the impacts of macroeconomic policies (Easy & Restrictive), domestic consumption, energy consumption on Ecological Footprint.
2. The present work provides the primary empirical work incorporating macroeconomic demand management policies, i.e., EFP and RFP and EMP and RMP related strategies, to check their ecological consequences.
3. No empirical evidence has yet analyzed the impacts of easy and restrictive demand management policies and ADC (aggregate per capita domestic consumption spending) on Ecological Footprint index for Asian Economies.

The paper is coordinated as follows. Section 2 is reserved for presenting the previous empirical work. Section 3 offers information about econometrics techniques and data sources. While section 4 outlines the results and discussion in detail. The final section offers the conclusion and policy recommendations.

Literature Review

The appropriate literature review can be ordered in the accompanying chapters: the ecological implications of Aggregate per capita domestic consumption spending (ADC), fossil fuel combustion (FFC), renewable energy consumption (REC), and macroeconomic policies. A brief empirical review of each component is given below.

Environmental implication of ADC

The Environmental Kuznets curve (EKC) theory depends on investigating the economic association of per capita Income and environmental contamination. The assumption places that contamination increments as an expanding pattern in per capita income, accepts a particular limit, eventually decreases; for instance, see Tausef Hasan et al. (2020), Sehidd and Ayddin (2019) and Acaravki and Ozturk (2010). This thought has been thoroughly affirmed for a few countries and territories throughout the most recent twenty years. Regarding the outcomes, these examinations can be ordered into two bundles. The primary pack records the examinations that approved the Environmental Kuznets Curve (EKC) theory Rehman et al., 2019; Javaid and Shareef 2016; &Naasir and Urr 2011 for Pakistan economy, Shahbaz and Senha 2018 for the Indian economy, Appergis et al. 2017 for US, Sepkota and Basstola 2017 for Latin America, Donge et al. 2017 for BRICS countries, Senha et al. 2017 for N-11 countries, Shahbaz et al., 2016 for African countries, Yang et al., 2015 for a group of 67 countries, Omre et al. 2015 for MENA countries, Niquaye and Oladdi 2015 for immature economies, Boutabba 2014 for Sub-Saharan African nations, and Lau et al., 2014; Sabore and Suleiman 2013 for the Malaysian economy. Then again, the subsequent pack records the investigations that did not confirm the presence of the environmental Kuznets curve hypothesis for chosen middle-income economies, Africa, 152 economies, Indian economy, OECD and NON-OECD countries, and for 22 Latin America and Caribbean nations (Arminin and Manegaki 2019, Zoundi 2017, Alaxandre et al. 2017, Senha and Restogi, 2017, Ozokcu and Ozdemir 2017 and Pablo-Romero and De Jesús, 2016).

Additional per capita Income, using the data from South Africa, Ahmad, and Khatak (2020) explored an item of Income (per capita) as a new forecaster of environmental degradation, i.e., ADC (aggregate per capita domestic consumption spending). The study results confirmed that aggregate per capita domestic consumption spending plays a crucial role in regulating environmental changes. Moreover, the demand puts excessive stress on business vendors for the rapid production of goods using many fossil fuels; after that, this procedure accelerates environmental degradation. As a less studied and essential provider to environmental quality, it is worth considering the consequences of aggregate per capita domestic consumption spending (ADC) on Chinese and Indian economies.

Environmental Consequences of Fossil Fuel Combustion

The following component of literature traces the observed connection between fossil fuel combustion and environmental quality. Even Though fossil fuel combustion is an essential component of economic growth, the current writing cautions about the unfriendly results of energy creation and consumption for physical quality (Urr and Rashed 2017). For instance, by taking the South African countries (Ahmad and Khatak (2020), for the panel of 67 upper-middle-income and high-income countries (Arminin and Manegaki (2019), for the chosen Asian nations Bhuiyan et al. (2018), for the Chinese economy, Ahmad et al. (2018), for Pakistan (Merza and Kanwall (2017), for SAARC countries (Urr and Rashed (2017), for OECD economies (Alvaraiz-Heranz et al. (2017), and for a basic illustration of overall economies (Zaman and Moemen (2017), explored the energy and environmental quality affiliation. The outcomes of all empirical literature state that a severe deal of energy ignition harms the climate by increasing the severe impacts of fossil fuel by environmental quality. Previously, JaforUllah and King (2017) and Itconen (2012) argued that the reconciliation of energy use in the model to

evaluate the environmental Kuznets curve thought might bring about a one-sided result. The substitution of energy used by fossil fuel combustion as a regressor can deliver firm conclusions (Arminin and Manegaki 2019).

Ecological Consequences of REC

In the third section, the empirical literature presents the unique climate impacts of renewable energy sources. In such a manner, numerous researchers investigated renewable energy consumption and environmental quality affiliation by considering the information for different nations and regions. The researchers maintain that renewable energy consumption is favorably associated with environmental quality by alleviating the disastrous environmental quality impacts. For instance, the empirical literature by Ikraam et al. (2020) on SAARC economies, Ullah et al. (2020) & Wahid et al. (2018) on Pakistan economy, Cheshti et al. (2020) for South Asian nations, Ahmad et al. (2019) for OECD countries, Bhattacharya et al., (2017) for the sample of chosen 85 developed nations, Jebble and Yousaf, (2017) for Tunisia, Belaed and Yousaf, (2017) for Algeria, Kais and Mounir, (2017) for the chosen nine high-income countries, and Bayrakcı and Kokar, (2012) for Turkey affirmed that ecological quality improves as the proportion of environmental quality will generally fall on account of utilization of renewable sources.

Ecological Consequences of Macroeconomic Policies

The final strand of literature centres around the recent determinants of environmental quality pointed out by Qingqun et al., 2020, namely EMP (easy monetary policy) and RMP (restrictive monetary policy). The empirical literature revealed that easy monetary policy makes the exigency of environmental quality increase; nonetheless, restrictive monetary policy is environmental-friendly as it reduces the environmental quality in Asian countries. Ultimately, scarcely a few empirical pieces of literature Ikei et al. (2020) accessible for Thailand, Yuilan et al. (2019) for the Chinese economy, Katirciouglu and Katirciouglu (2018) for Turkey, and the Halkous and Paezanos (2016) for the US economy, which explored the impacts of monetary policy on environmental quality. Notwithstanding, these bits of proof do not consider the easy and restrictive parts of the monetary approach that convey critical effects on economic activity (Cannh, 2018; Mankiw, 2003). Thus, it is essential to consider the ecological implication of both easy and restrictive monetary policies concerning Chinese and Indian economies.

The review of empirical work reveals few studies to check the impact of fiscal policy on environmental quality. However, the novelty of the present study lies in the contribution towards the existing literature that presents the primary macroeconomic model, which investigates the impacts of both EMP (easy monetary policy) and RMP (restrictive monetary policy) on environmental quality. Furthermore, again as far as we could know, no distributed work has yet analyzed the impacts of easy and restrictive monetary policy and aggregate per capita domestic consumption spending on environmental quality for Chinese and Indian economies. Hence, it is essential to consider the ecological implication of both easy and restrictive monetary policies by employing the ECFP to measure environmental quality for Chinese and Indian economies.

Variable's description and data Sources

All selected indicators of the present study are collected from the WDI (World Development Indicators) from 1985 to 2019 of Chinese and Indian economies. The present empirical analysis contains the coincident indicators: environmental quality (ECFP) as an indicator of environmental quality, real interest rate (r) as an indicator of monetary policy, tax revenues (RT) as a percentage of the gross domestic product as an indicator of fiscal policy, FFC (fossil fuel combustion), REC, and ADC. The data for ECFP index is extracted from Global Footprint network (2021). The data for all other variables are collected from world development indicators (WDI).

$$\text{ADC is equal to } \frac{\text{GDP} + (\text{NX})}{\text{TP}}$$

Where:

GDP → Gross Domestic Product

NX → exports - imports

TP → total population

Empirical Methodology and Results

The present article incorporates the five-step procedure to derive the empirical estimates. The first step is related to check for the cross-sectional dependence (CD) test proposed by Pesaran, Friedman, and frees. Second step employing the panel unit root tests (Levine Lin Chu & Im Pesaran Shin) to check the stationarity of the variables. The third step was to check for long-run affiliation among the variables by utilizing the Westerlund tests. The fourth step is concerned with the estimation of the long-run coefficients by incorporating the two steps system GMM (generalized method of Moment) model. Finally, to check the relationship's direction among the variables, the GC (granger causality) test is utilized. The results of the descriptive statistics of the variables are placed in table 1.

Table: 1 Descriptive Statistics of the Variables

	ECFP	R	RT	FFC	REC	ADC
Mean	1.78	10.29	12.40	67.16	24.85	7.81
Median	0.91	3.84	13.17	83.48	17.72	7.34
Max.	5.25	76.72	29.45	91.38	52.67	8.89
Min.	0.05	16.59	2.76	52.13	2.72	5.42
St. dev	2.46	16.39	5.37	12.71	15.68	0.49
Skewness	2.17	1.27	1.48	- 0.16	0.41	- 0.46
Kurtosis	1.89	4.26	2.17	2.38	1.35	2.39
Jb.	27.34	91.38	15.03	13.02	10.80	13.21
Prob.	0.0002	0.0000	0.0012	0.0028	0.0009	0.0008

The maximum and minimum values of the selected variables show a significant difference, noticeable variations, and trends, particularly R (real interest rate) and RT (tax revenues). Moreover, the results indicate that environmental quality (ECFP), real interest rate, tax revenues, and renewable energy consumption are positively skewed (future data points of these variables will be more than their mean values). Further, the fossil fuel combustion and aggregate per capita domestic consumption spending indicate that their estimated future data point will be less than their average value (negatively skewed). In contrast, the real rate of interest represents the leptokurtic distribution as its value is reported as more than three. On the Contrary value of environmental quality, tax revenues, fossil fuel combustion, and aggregate per capita domestic consumption spending represent the platykurtic distribution as their value is less than three. The outcome of skewness and kurtosis indicates that all variables are dismissed for being normally distributed. This way, the Jarque-Bera test affirmed the outcomes. These results support the idea to utilize quantitative methods, as shown in the following section.

Results of Unit root tests

Before going to apply the stationarity test here it is important first to check for the cross-sectional dependence test. The CD test results are reported in table 2. The null hypothesis of the test is that there is no cross-sectional dependence. The results indicated the existence of cross-sectional dependence. As all of three tests failed to accept the null hypothesis. So, the stationarity properties of the variables, we have to utilize the second-generation panel unit root tests (CIPS & CADF). Results of the unit root test are reported in table 3. The tests reveal that all the variables are non-stationary at their level and become stationary after taking the first difference. Results of the tests confirmed the stationarity of all the panels reported in table 3. Further, it also observed that all the panels are stationarity at a one per cent significance level.

Table: 2 Unit Root Test Results

Test	Statistics	Probability	Decision
Pesaran	3.09	0.03	Cross sectional Dependence
Friedman	27.65	0.01	Cross sectional Dependence
Frees	9.67	0.03	Cross sectional Dependence

Table: 3 Unit Root Test Results

	ECFP	R	RT	FFC	REC	ADC
CADF						
I (0)	1.71	1.82	0.76	1.78	1.91	2.90
I (1)	4.57**	3.59**	5.02**	4.35**	3.60**	6.96**
CIPS						
I (0)	0.98	1.60	0.57	1.05	1.73	1.05
I (1)	7.67**	4.81**	7.51**	6.29**	5.47**	7.41**

Note: ** shows the stationarity at 1% significance level

Panel Cointegration Analysis

To answer the presence of panel cointegration among the selected variables, we utilize the test Westerlund (2005), with the null hypothesis being no cointegration among the scrutinized variables due to the existence of cross-sectional dependence (see Table 4). It is vital to give extra cointegration testing, demonstrating the robustness for structural breaks and cross-sectional dependence. The outcomes of Westerlund tests introduced in Table 4 propose that dependent on the critical bootstrapped values, three out of four tests reject the no

cointegration null hypothesis. These findings further affirm the long-run cointegration among the variables (see table 5).

Table:4 Results of Westerlund Cointegration Test

Statistics	Values	Z-Value	P-Value
G_t	-2.78	5.71	0.004
G_a	2.318	9.73	0.635
P_t	-2.03	8.52	0.003
P_a	-0.783	11.81	0.005

Note: The G_a and G_t test statistics are to test $H_0: \alpha_i = 0$ for all i whereas the $H_a: \alpha_i < 0$ for at least one i . In addition, the P_a and P_t test statistics implying pool information over all the cross-sectional units with $H_0: \alpha_i = 0$ for all I whereas the $H_a: \alpha_i < 0$ for at least one i

Estimation of the Long run Coefficients

We utilized two steps System GMM technique to estimate the long-run coefficients. Long-run results of the estimated coefficients from the above-mentioned econometric techniques are reported in table 5.

Table: 5 Long run Estimates

	Coefficients	Probability
$ECFP_{t-1}$	1.36	0.000
EFP	0.63 (1.20)	0.021
RFP	- 0.71 (2.15)	0.014
EMP	0.39 (1.98)	0.000
RMP	- 0.61 (2.87)	0.017
ADC	0.88 (1.98)	0.000
FFC	0.69 (2.79)	0.031
REC	- 0.62 (3.69)	0.000

Diagnostic Test

Arellano Bond

AR (1) → -2.52 (0.002)

AR (2) → -0.67 (0.434)

Wald → 379.13 (0.000)

Sargan → 6.96 (Prob. 1)

Source: Own Elaboration

The result of ordinary least square two steps system GMM model shows an expansion of 1% in the easy fiscal strategy (EFP); the share of environmental quality in the Asian economies is adopted at 0.63%. The presumed illustration is that the Asian countries have been trying for a long time to acquire sustainable development and deal with the requirements of inflation, unemployment. Progress due to extraordinary contraction (2007 to 2009). likewise, EFP is being implemented in these economies by reducing tax revenues and expanding government spending, expanding uses to modernize the ADC, revitalize the modern region, and increase employment. Thus, it is evident that the surge in modern creativity due to the expansion of ADC has led to the rise of environmental quality. Another opportunity is that the new industrialists prefer modest and chaotic unclean sources to clean energy sources during financial disasters. After that, a high percentage of carbon dioxide equivalent is exhaled.

Then again, the environmental quality diminishes by 0.71 due to a 1% increase in RFP (restrictive fiscal policy). Economies worldwide appear to be implementing restrictive fiscal policy to cope with inflation after exceeding their set cutoff, which is seen as sound for economic advancement. Moreover, as a specific approach measure, some countries practice raising general prices by 2% each year to aid in financial exercises. In this way, the consumer anticipates an increase in item prices in the coming future and will broaden the buying today. This excessive demand is pressuring the production side to satisfy excess demand. If the manufacturers cannot produce to meet the excessive demand, they are obligated to increase the prices. Alternatively, Else may expand the production capability by hiring more workers, which means increased employment and increased spending. Progress in this cycle can create a significant degree of expansion, which can be detrimental to the economy. To deal with a fundamental circumstance, governments often raise the tax rates and cut their spending. The raw materials became expensive by imposing a high tax ratio, reducing production, aggregate per capita domestic consumption spending, national income, and environmental quality. These outcomes are new as they clarify the relationship between EFP and RFP (fiscal policy) and environmental quality.

Besides, the consequences of long-run relationship between EMP (easy monetary policy) and environmental quality. It infers that 1% ascent in the easy monetary policy expands environmental quality by 0.39%. A comparative result is revealed for considering the selected Asian economies by Qingquan et al. (2020). Potentially, alongside taking different measures, the central bank likes to select an easy monetary policy to manage specific monetary issues like poverty, unemployment, and downturn. The easy monetary policy improves the monetary advancement by encouraging the output of the modern sector and reducing unemployment, which extends the fossil fuel utilization; thus, it prompts an expansion in the severe impacts of environmental quality.

The coefficients of system GMM model divulge that environmental quality diminishes by 0.61%, as the monetary policy shrunk by 1% in Chinese and Indian economies. Our results are per Qingquan et al. (2020), who found an inverse relationship between environmental quality and restrictive monetary policy for Asian nations. The conceivable explanation is that central banks carry out the restrictive monetary policy in the circumstance of painful high inflation resulting from excessive demand. To improve the impeding effects of inflation, central banks increment the interest rate, which makes the advance from banks exorbitant and less productive. Appropriately, this execution frustrates the creation of products, employment, national income, and environmental quality.

The estimates of a significant long-run association between the ADC (aggregate per capita domestic consumption spending) and environmental quality. These results pointed out that ADC adds to crumble the natural quality by expanding environmental quality. The result indicates that a one per cent increase in ADC (aggregate per capita domestic consumption spending) tends to increase the environmental quality by 0.88%. Similar outcomes were additionally detailed by Ahmad and Khattak (2020) on account of South Africa. An increase in ADC produces an excess demand, which supports the producers for more production by utilizing cheap environmentally unfriendly techniques. Ultimately, this interaction deteriorates the environmental quality by increasing environmental quality.

Further, all employed methods confirmed the existence of significant long-run affiliation between fossil fuel combustion and environmental quality. It observed that one percent change in fossil fuel combustion brings 0.69 % increase in environmental quality. The results are consistent with the finding of Ahmad and Khattak (2020), Hanif et al., & Mensah et al. (2019), Appiah, Asareh and Nedae (2018), and Dar and Asif (2017), among others. Additionally, the results of the tests confirmed the existence of an adverse but significant relationship between renewable energy consumption and environmental quality. It signifies that one percent change in REC brings 0.62% fall in environmental quality, respectively. The results are consistent with the findings of Ahmad al. & Chen et al., and Nathaniel & Iheonu (2019), and Wahid et al. (2018).

Further, to check the direction of association among the selected variables GC (Granger Causality) test is utilized. The results of the test confirmed the existence of causality among different variables. Results of the GC test are placed in table 6. Results pointed out one-way causality between fiscal policy (easy and restrictive), monetary policy (easy and restrictive), and environmental quality. Further, following the outcomes of Ahamad and Khattak (2019), Belaed and Yousaf (2017) result pointed out one-way causality among ADC, renewable energy consumption, and environmental quality.

Table: 6 Findings of GC Test

Null Hypothesis	F-Stat.	Direction of relationship
Easy fiscal policy does not GC ECFP ECFP does not GC Easy fiscal policy	16.25** 1.20	Easy Fiscal Policy → CO ₂
Restrictive fiscal policy does not GC ECFP ECFP does not GC Restrictive fiscal policy	11.27** 1.68	Restrictive Fiscal Policy → CO ₂
Easy monetary policy does not GC ECFP ECFP does not GC Easy monetary policy	14.70** 2.62	Easy Monetary Policy → CO ₂
Restrictive monetary policy does not GC ECFP ECFP does not GC Restrictive monetary policy	17.01** 1.27	Restrictive Monetary Policy → CO ₂
ADC does not GC ECFP ECFP does not GC ADC	9.30*** 0.92	ADC → CO ₂
REC does not GC ECFP ECFP does not GC REC	6.35*** 2.15	REC → CO ₂

FFC does not GC ECFP ECFP does not GC FFC	14.63** 1.66	FFC → CO ₂
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Note **and *** shows the level of significance at 1% and 5% respectively

Conclusion and policy Recommendation

The motivation behind the article was to review the potential macroeconomic linkages among fiscal policy & Monetary policy (easy and restrictive) and environmental quality, with the partner of some control factors, i.e., ADC, FFC (fossil fuel combustion) and REC, for Asian economies. The utilization of Westerlund cointegration tests affirms long-run affiliation among the selected variables. As per the long-run results of system GMM, EFP (easy fiscal policy) distorts the ecological quality by flooding the impending impacts of environmental quality RFP (restrictive fiscal policy) reduces the environmental quality. Moreover, easy monetary policy (EMP) and restrictive monetary policy (RMP) likewise add to and upset ecological contamination by expanding and diminishing environmental quality, respectively. Moreover, the results declared a positive relationship between aggregate per capita domestic consumption spending (ADC) and Environmental quality except for the OLS method's result. In addition, fossil fuel combustion (FFC) and REC weaken and improve climatic quality by expanding and diminishing Environmental quality, respectively.

Further, the results of the GC test confirmed the existence of a one-way relationship between fiscal policy, monetary policy, ADC, fossil fuel combustion, renewable energy consumption, and environmental quality. Based on the empirical findings of the present study, the following policy implications are suggested.

1. Initially, the new results set the requirement for specialists and governments to extend 'green fiscal and monetary-related strategies' in Chinese and Indian economies. The outcomes reveal that easy fiscal policy (EFP) prompts to accelerate, while restrictive fiscal policy (RFP) prompts to reduce the degree of environmental quality. However, policymakers should make policies in such a way to launch the green subsidy and tax programs to improve the environmental quality.
2. Further, the effect of monetary policy suggested that central banks should practice the concept of green lending rates for commercial banks to enhance environmental quality.
3. Moreover, the significant positive affiliation between aggregate per capita domestic consumption spending and environmental quality suggested that policymakers should devote a considerable share of their budget towards research and development regarding the promotion of environmentally friendly techniques.
4. Lastly, the relationship between fossil fuel combustion, renewable energy consumption, and environmental quality pointed out that government and policymakers should start programs to educate investors on using the latest technology available.

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